

PREPARATION OF POLY(LACTIC ACID)-VATERITE HYBRID MEMBRANES FOR GUIDED BONE REGENERATION

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SUMMARY

A novel membrane for guided bone regeneration was developed using poly(L-lactide acid) (PLA)/siloxane-containing vaterite hybrid material (Si-PVH) by an electrospinning method. The Si-PVH fibers were covered with hydroxyapatite by soaking in simulated body fluid. The Si-PVH cloth was bonded with a PLA cloth for the barrier of soft tissue intrusion.

Keywords: Biomaterials, Nonwoven, Poly(lactic acid), Vaterite, Guided bone regeneration

INTRODUCTION

Guided bone regeneration (GBR) is a well-established therapy to repair alveolar bone defects. GBR reconstructs new bone using a barrier membrane to guard the defected area from invasion of other tissues. Recently, many researchers have investigated on the membranes that are biodegradable materials, such as collagen and synthetic biodegradable polymers.

We have already reported that the poly(L-lactic acid) (PLA)-based hybrid materials containing vaterite, which is one of the polymorphs in calcium carbonates, have much higher hydroxyapatite (HA)-forming ability in simulated body fluid (SBF) than conventional composites containing calcium phosphates.[1] Hereafter, the materials are denoted by PVH (Poly(lactic acid)/Vaterite Hybrids). HA coating, which shows effective biocompatibility, on PVH utilizing excellent forming ability in SBF has an effect on improvement in the biocompatibility of PVH.

Hench *et al.* suggested that the stimulation of bone formation on Bioglass® originates from the stimulatory effect of silicon and calcium ions released from the material and osteoblasts are activated genetically by these ions mediated by insulin-like growth factor II.[2] The incorporation of silicon species into biomaterials may play an important role in the preparation of materials with excellent bone-forming ability.

In our group, some polymer-ceramic composites and hybrids with silicon-species releasing ability were prepared [3-6] and reported to stimulate cellular activities, such as the proliferation and the differentiation of murine osteoblast-like cells, the

mineralization of human osteoblasts and the osteogenic differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells [7].

Recently, we have developed a novel hybrid material consisting of poly(L-lactic acid) (PLA) and calcium carbonate (vaterite) particles doped with siloxane [8]. Hereafter, the material is denoted by Si-PVH (Siloxane-doped Poly(L-lactic acid)/Vaterite Hybrids). In the material, siloxane is included in vaterite particles of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter; at the surface of the particles, the siloxane is bonded to a carboxy group in PLA matrix phase through amide-I bond and the Ca^{2+} ion around the surface is coordinated with the carboxy group [8].

GBR membranes should have the function to control the intrusion of soft tissue, the surface roughness for integration with the surrounding tissues for enhancing their stabilization (*i.e.*, tissue integration), the high mechanical strength to keep the space of the bone defect for the new bone reconstruction, and the function to enhance the bone formation [9, 10].

An electrospinning method is useful for forming the nonwoven cloths of polymers with connective pores. In the present work, an electrospun Si-PVH nonwoven cloth was successfully prepared, and bonded with a PLA nonwoven cloth for the barrier of soft tissue intrusion to prepare a new type of bi-layered GBR membrane.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Siloxane-doped vaterite (Si-V) powders were prepared by a carbonation process with methanol.[8] A 150 g of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, 60 ml of aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) and 2000 ml of methanol were mixed with blowing CO_2 gas for 75 min at a rate of $2000 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The resulting slurry was dried at 110°C , resulting in the formation of spherical-shaped Si-V powders with an average particle size of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$. The amount of silicon in Si-V was estimated from X-ray fluorescence analysis to be $\sim 3 \text{ wt}\%$.

The PLA and Si-V were kneaded by a mechanically mixing machine, resulting in the formation of Si-PVH. The weight ratio of Si-V to PLA was 3/2. A 28 g of PLA (PURASORB[®] PL24, molecular weights; $M_w = 200\sim 300 \text{ kDa}$) and 42 g of Si-V powders were kneaded at 200°C for 10 min.

The nonwoven cloths of Si-PVH and PLA were prepared by an electrospinning method under the conditions of the charge density; 20 kV, a flow rate of $0.05 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and distance from a nozzle to a collector; 150 mm. A solution for the electrospinning was prepared using chloroform as solvent. The weight ratios of PLA in the solution were 10 and 9 wt% for the formation of the Si-PVH nonwoven cloth and the PLA one, respectively.

The PLA cloth was bonded with the Si-PVH one by a hot-pressing method. The square-shaped PLA cloth of $15 \text{ mm}\times 15 \text{ mm}$ was placed on the same-sized Si-PVH one, and then pressed at $\sim 0.2 \text{ MPa}$ with a stainless steel mesh (the opening size of $\sim 400 \mu\text{m}$) heated at 150°C for 10 sec, resulting in the formation of the bi-layered membrane. The structural morphology of the bi-layered membrane was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

To be coated with hydroxyapatite, the Si-PVH or bi-layered membranes was soaked in simulated body fluid (SBF) consisting of 3.75 mM of Ca^{2+} , 213.0 mM of Na^+ , 2.25 mM

of Mg^{2+} , 7.5 mM of K^+ , 223.2 mM of Cl^- , 6.3 mM of HCO_3^- , 1.5 mM of HPO_4^{2-} , and 0.75 mM of SO_4^{2-} , adjusted at pH 7.4 by including $(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_3\text{CNH}_2$ and HCl, at 37°C for 24 h.

Silicon releasability of the Si-PVH cloth before and after HA-coating (the sample coated with HA is denoted by Si-PVH-HA, hereafter) were evaluated by immersing them in 4 ml of a culture medium (alpha minimum essential medium, α -MEM) containing 10 % foetal bovine serum (FBS) and incubated at 37°C in humidified atmosphere of 95 % air and 5 % CO_2 for 5 days. The size of the used sample was 10 x 10 mm. The culture medium was changed after 1 and 3 days of soaking, assuming the process of the cell-culture test. The amount of silicon-species released from the samples in the culture medium was measured by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES).

Mouse osteoblast-like (MC3T3-E1) cells were seeded onto the Si-PVH-HA cloth which placed in 24-well plates, at a density of 30,000 cells/well. α -MEM containing 10% FBS was used as a culture medium. The medium was replaced after 1 day-culturing and then replaced every other day. The cells were fixed with 2.5% glutaraldehyde, and then dehydrated with ethanol, and finally dried with hexamethyldisilazane.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the SEM micrographs of the Si-PVH nonwoven cloth prepared by an electrospinning method. In the present work the Si-PVH cloths of 150 ~ 250 μm in thickness were successfully prepared. These cloths consist of the fibers with the size of ~10 μm in diameter. The pores, of which sizes are several tens to hundreds μm , formed by entangling the fibers in the cloth may be effective in bone-in-growth. The Si-PVH cloth, however, shows slightly brittleness, which originates from the inclusion of a large amount of vaterite particle (60 % in weight).

After the Si-PVH cloth was soaked in a modified SBF at 37°C for 1 day, the surface of the fiber was completely covered with leaf-like products, as shown in Fig. 2(a). The products are identified from x-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis to be HA, as shown in Fig. 2(b). No significant change is observed in the gap sizes between the microfibers before and after soaking. The HA formed on the microfibers directly and tightly contacted to their surfaces, since it adhered on their surfaces after the flexibility tests using a pair of tweezers.

Figure 3 shows the amount of silicon ion released from both the Si-PVH and Si-PVH-HA cloths into the culture medium. A concentration of 8.2 mg/L of ionic silicon species were released from the Si-PVH cloth in 1 day. The Si-PVH-HA cloth was then soaked in the culture medium after being incubated in SBF for 1 day and coated with HA significantly reduced with only 0.68 mg/L of the species released from the cloth in 1 day of soaking in the medium. After the HA-coating, an initial burst dissolution of the silicon-species from the Si-PVH cloth was controlled, while the cloth generated the releasability of a trace amount of the species in the culture medium for 5 days.

Fig.1. SEM micrograph of the Si-PVH nonwoven cloth.

Fig. 2. SEM micrograph and XRD pattern of the Si-PVH-HA.

Fig. 3. Silicon ion concentration in culture media after soaking Si-PVH or Si-PVH-HA cloths.

The Si-PVH fibers with sizes of 0.5 ~ 20 μm in diameter have been prepared in our preliminary experiments. Their diameters were controllable by changing the conditions on the electrospinning, such as the PLA concentration in the solution and solvent. In the present work, the composite microfibers with 10 μm in diameter were used as the samples for the cell culture tests, because we hypothesized that the spaces between the microfibers provide the scaffolds for the cell proliferation. After the MC3T3-E1 cell culture test, the numerous cells were observed on the microfibers in the Si-PVH-HA cloth after 1 day-culturing. The cells elongated on the surfaces of the microfibers and some of them entered the cloth.

In our previous work, the proliferation and differentiation of MC3T3-E1 cells were enhanced on a dense film consisting of Si-V and PLA composites.[8] In addition, human osteoblasts and mesenchymal stem cells were stimulated to mineralize and differentiate on siloxane-doped PLA and vaterite hybrid membranes which released a trace amount of silicon-species.[11] Reffitt *et al.* reported that approximately 0.3 ~ 0.6 mg/L of orthosilicic acid in a culture medium were reported to be effective to stimulate collagen type I synthesis and osteoblastic differentiation in human osteoblast-like cells.[12] These amounts are considerably similar with that of silicon species reported in the present work. The Si-PVH-HA cloth may become good candidates for enhancing the cell activation and the bone formation.

Figure 4 shows the SEM micrograph of the PLA nonwoven cloth prepared by an electrospinning method. The thickness of the as-prepared PLA cloth was also 150~250 μm . The PLA cloths with excellent flexibility and mechanical strength to allow easy handling could be prepared. The PLA cloth may have no effect on bone formation, but they are expected to control the soft tissue intrusion by adjusting the pore sizes in them and to generate tissue integration.

The PLA cloth was pressed at the pressure of 15 MPa at room temperature, and then the sizes of opening spaces between the fibers were reduced for the purpose of controlling the intrusion of soft tissues.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of the PLA nonwoven cloth.

Fig. 5. SEM micrograph of the PLA nonwoven cloth after the pressing.

Figure 5 shows the SEM micrograph of the pressed PLA cloth. The thickness after the pressing was reduced to 50~100 μm . Almost no significant change in the shapes of the fibers by the pressing was seen, but the sizes of spaces formed by entangling the fibers were significantly decreased. The PLA cloth showed excellent flexibility and slight stretching due to the deformation of the entangling fibers; it was not broken easily by pulling by hands. The cloth has much stronger mechanically than Si-PVH one.

Figure 6 shows the cross-sectional SEM micrographs of the resulting bi-layered membrane consisting of the Si-PVH nonwoven cloth and the pressed PLA one. The thickness of the membrane was 80~200 μm . Two types of the cloths were successfully bonded. The resulting bi-layered membrane showed excellent flexibility enough to easily bend with tweezers. At the bonded portion by the local hot-pressing using a stainless steel mesh, the PLA fibers and the Si-PVH fibers were partially melted, and almost no borders between the PLA and Si-PVH cloth layers were seen.

Figure 7 shows the SEM micrographs of the cloth surfaces. The PLA fibers were melted at the hot-pressed portions. Although the shapes of the Si-PVH fibers were almost changed, the spaces between the Si-PVH fibers around the bonded portions narrowed.

In the bi-layered membrane, some of the PLA and Si-PVH fibers around the bonded portions were partially melted, resulting in the formation of their strong connections. The porous structure in each cloth was not broken except the bonded portions.

As described above, the Si-PVH nonwoven cloth has a disadvantage in the mechanical strength; it is easily broken by pulling by hands. This brittleness originates from that the Si-PVH includes a large amount of Si-V (60 wt%). When numerous vaterite particles are embedded in PLA matrix, the resulting composites have been reported to show mechanical brittleness.[1] In the present membrane, the brittleness of the Si-PVH cloth was significantly improved by being bonded with the PLA cloth.

After soaking the bi-layered membrane in SBF, the surfaces of the Si-PVH fibers were completely covered with HA, as well as the single layer consisting of the Si-PVH nonwoven cloth shown in Fig. 2. The thickness of the hydroxyapatite layer on the fiber was estimated from the diameter of the original fiber to be $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$. On the other hand, no hydroxyapatite formation occurred on the PLA fibers in the membrane.

The results of implantation in New Zealand white rabbits for 3 months has been reported in elsewhere.[13] New bone formation was observed in the Si-PVH layer, predominantly at around the bonded portions. No intrusion of soft tissues and no inflammation were observed. These results may indicate that the PLA fibers layer intercepted the intrusion of soft tissues and the Si-PVH one induced the bone formation.

The large spaces formed by the fibers in the nonwoven cloth are not expected to control the intrusion of soft tissues. The sizes of the spaces in the PLA layer were reduced by pressing at room temperature. The layer is suggested to play an important role in controlling the intrusion of the soft tissue. The surface of the pressed PLA layer is estimated from the diameters of the fibers to be relatively large roughness of several tens μm , as shown in Fig. 5; the layer is also expected to play an important role in the generation of tissue integration.

Fig. 6. Cross-sectional SEM micrographs of the bi-layered membrane.

Thus, the preparation method of the bi-layered membrane in the present work is suitable for making full use of the active functions in the PLA and Si-PVH cloths. No deformation and disintegration of the membrane after 12 weeks of the *in vivo* implantation were observed.[13] The bi-layered membrane in the present work is expected to be applicable to the GBR treatment.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Nonwoven cloths of ~200- μm thickness of poly(L-lactide acid) (PLA)/siloxane-containing vaterite hybrid material (Si-PVH) were prepared by an electrospinning method. The surfaces of the Si-PVH fibers were completely covered with hydroxyapatite by soaking in simulated body fluid for 1 day. The cloths coated with HA

Fig. 7. SEM micrographs for the surfaces of the bi-layered membrane.

released 0.2 -0.7 mg/L of silicon species in a cell culture medium for 7 days. A trace amount of silicon-species has been reported to enhance the mineralization and bone-forming abilities of osteogenic cells. Osteoblast-like MC3T3-E1 cells elongated on the microfibers of the cloths and some of them entered the mesh after 1 day-culturing. The Si-PVH cloth was successfully bonded with a PLA cloth to prepare a new type of bi-layered GBR membrane. The first layer consists of an Si-PVH cloth with large-sized pores for enhancing bone formation, and the second layer consists of a PLA cloth with small-sized pores for controlling the intrusion of soft tissues and for reinforcing the mechanical strength of the brittle Si-PVH layer. The bi-layered membrane was implanted; the Si-PVH cloth was placed in contact with 8 mm in diameter hole drilled in calvaria of 14-week old rabbits and the PLA cloth was placed in contact with the skin; new bone formation was observed in the Si-PVH layer. The result showed that the PLA fibers layer interrupted the intrusion of soft tissues and the Si-PVH one induced the bone formation. The bi-layered membrane is expected to be effective in GBR treatment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported in part by Grant-in-Aids for Scientific Research from Japan Society for Promotion of Science (Nos. 20390497 and 21700487).

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